

Educating Patriotism for Students According to Ho Chi Minh's Ideology

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Abstract:

Patriotism education in the current context is one of the important solutions to build new socialist people to meet the requirements of the cause of building and protecting the Fatherland. The 13th National Congress of the Party emphasized: "Pay more attention to educating morality, personality, creative capacity and core values, especially educating the spirit of patriotism, pride, and self-esteem." National respect, national traditions and history a sense of social responsibility for all classes of people, especially the younger

generation. The Vietnamese people have a passionate patriotic tradition. That tradition is always preserved and promoted by everyone. That is the red thread that determines all victories of the nation.

Keywords: *Patriotism, students, education.*

Introduction

Patriotism is a unique feature of our country's long-standing culture, it has been expressed from time immemorial and goes deep into every action and thought of every person. Patriotism is to love all that is good, to love nature in all its forms, to love the clear blue sky, to love flocks of flying birds, to love even dear or close rivers, and to love fragile leaves. After all, patriotism comes from the will, determination to strive, build the Fatherland, love and hope. Patriotism includes many other loves: love of family, homeland, love of people. It is revealed anytime, anywhere, in every individual, wherever Vietnamese people live, it will forever be a fire, a bud of Vietnamese patriotism. When the country is independent and peaceful, our entire nation will enter the work of building a developed country. Society is progressing day by day, everything has changed a lot, only the patriotism of each individual has not faded. In life, ideas and actions help develop the country's

economy, partly demonstrating the spirit of patriotism. From farmers with dirty hands and hands, still as simple as ever, they produce rice grains to serve agriculture and each individual's life. Or the doctors who wholeheartedly help patients, the teachers who diligently teach children, the soldiers who guard the borders and islands... these are also gestures of kindness and sacrifice for a great cause, love for people, and more broadly, the spirit of patriotism.

Results and Discussion

Ho Chi Minh's Ideology on Patriotic Education for the Young Generation

With a spirit of curiosity and learning, with independent and creative thinking, President Ho Chi Minh soon formed a great ambition and was determined to find his own path. He highly respected and admired the indomitable fighting spirit of previous patriots, but he believed that Mr. Phan Boi Chau's journey to the East was no

different from "chasing tigers at the front door, receiving leopards at the back door". While Mr. Phan Chu Trinh carried out reformist measures, it was like "asking the enemy for mercy". People do not follow the path their predecessors took, but have different thoughts and different ways. Regarding his purpose of going abroad, in 1923 he answered the Russian journalist Osip Mandenxtam: "When I was about thirteen years old, for the first time I heard the three French words Freedom, Equality, Fraternity... I really want to get acquainted with French civilization, want to find out what is hidden behind those words. Another time, responding to an American writer, he said: "The Vietnamese people, including my father, often wonder who will help them escape French rule. Some people think it's England, some people think it's America. I felt I had to go abroad to see more clearly. After seeing how they are doing, I will return to help my people". Thus, President Ho Chi Minh's ambition to find a way to save the country is completely different from his predecessors. Clearly, he soon realized that "what the nation needs first is not guns, ammunition, or wealth, but a way to expel the enemy and save the country, to make a revolution, or in other words, revolutionary theory and methods.

It was patriotism that brought President Ho Chi Minh to that wonderful meeting with Lenin's thought. It created a fundamental change for him - a young revolutionary soldier and began a real change in the history of our country's revolutionary ideology - "completely believing in Lenin, believing in the Third International". President Ho Chi Minh steadily stepped forward to attend the 18th Congress of the French Socialist Party in Tours city. At this Congress, he joined with famous French political and cultural activists such as: Marcel Cachin, Paul Vaillant Couturier... to defend Marxism, against the opportunist. Also at this Congress, he voted to endorse the Third International, becoming one of the founders of the French Communist Party. It was dawn on December 30, 1920. At that moment, the first Vietnamese communist, Nguyen Ai Quoc, appeared. That moment marked the event when President Ho Chi Minh

moved from true patriotism to Leninism and determined to follow the light of Leninist thought. He finally found a path of liberation that not only broke the chains for the Vietnamese people but also served as a common hope for other colonial peoples around the world.

According to Ho Chi Minh, patriotism is the highest value in the scale of traditional Vietnamese values. He affirmed: "Our people have a passionate patriotism. It is a precious tradition of ours. From ancient times until now, every time the Fatherland was invaded, that spirit was excited, it formed an extremely strong and huge wave, it swept over all dangers and difficulties, it engulfed everything both those who sell the country and those who steal the country. In addition to moral knowledge, moral feelings are also an important content in moral education. Therefore, in moral education for young people, in addition to moral values, Ho Chi Minh also paid special attention to fostering moral feelings. He affirmed that the most important mission of the school is "to teach students to love the country and their race. We must teach them the will to be independent, self-reliant, determined not to be inferior to anyone, determined not to be slaves."

President Ho Chi Minh called for: "Our youth actively volunteer to try to fulfill their leading duties in all fields of economic, cultural, and defense activities, implementing the slogan that youth are not needed, nor is it difficult." there are young people". Vietnamese youth must have strong political courage, be imbued with Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's ideology and have faith in the socialist regime: "Loving the Fatherland and loving the people must be associated with love socialism". Therefore, educating political bravery, determination to realize the goal of "national independence associated with socialism" and belief in the Vietnamese revolution are very important contents in educating patriotism for young people. President Ho Chi Minh generalized the most common standards of revolutionary ethics: Loyalty to the country, filial piety to the people; Love people; Diligence, frugality, integrity, righteousness, public-mindedness and

impartiality; Pure international spirit. The moral qualities proposed by him are very diverse, suitable for each subject, but the core, most important and comprehensive is the moral qualities of "loyalty to the country, filial piety to the people". "Loyalty" and "filial piety" are categories that exist in traditional Vietnamese moral thought in particular and the East in general.

According to Ho Chi Minh, "loyalty to the country" means, first of all, having patriotism, all thoughts and actions are directed towards serving the Fatherland and serving the people; Anything contrary to the interests of the Fatherland and the people should be avoided as much as possible; Resolutely and persistently fight against all actions that violate the interests of the country and people. Loyalty to the Party means always being loyal to the Party's ideals, having absolute confidence in the Party's leadership and good compliance with the Party's guidelines and policies, the State's policies and laws. "Filial to the people" means respecting, loving parents, and loving people; love and respect the people, study, work, fight for the people, always try to do things that benefit the country and the people.

Current Status of Patriotic Education for Students

The Political Report at the 12th National Congress of the Party clearly stated the tasks to promote the youth force are: Innovating the content and methods of political education, ideology, ideals, traditions system; foster revolutionary ideals and patriotism; building ethics, healthy lifestyle, awareness of respect and strict observance of the constitution and law for the young generation; have appropriate mechanisms and policies to create a favorable environment and conditions for the young generation to study, research, work, entertain and develop intelligence, skills and physical strength; Encourage and encourage young people to nurture dreams, ambitions, be proactive, creative and master modern science and technology; promote the role of the young generation in the cause of building and protecting the Fatherland...

Patriotism is a natural human feeling towards the homeland, its language, culture, history and good traditions. It can be understood that patriotism is love for the homeland, the country and the spirit of willingness to use all one's abilities to serve the interests of the Fatherland. Along with the formation of the nation and the national state, patriotism from an emotion, a socio-psychological factor has gradually evolved into a social consciousness. Once that consciousness has developed into a system, patriotic sentiment has the potential to become patriotism - valuable as an ideology.

So, patriotism is "Ethical and political principles, a social sentiment whose content is love and loyalty to the Fatherland, pride in the Fatherland's past and present, will protect the interests of the Fatherland". Thus, patriotism is a category in the field of social consciousness, including the thoughts and feelings of a nation. The main content of patriotism is love and loyalty to the Fatherland.

The formation of patriotism has many causes, but focuses on two basic causes: the first is the struggle against harsh natural disasters, the second is the struggle against foreign invaders. The basic content of patriotism of the Vietnamese people is expressed in feelings of attachment to the homeland and country; love for fellow races and nations; legitimate national pride; united and indomitable to fight foreign invaders, protect national sovereignty and the independence and freedom of the Fatherland; diligence and creativity in working to build and develop national culture and build an increasingly rich and beautiful country.

Educating patriotism for the young generation must start from educating them to be aware of the love of homeland, country, and socialist consciousness, which are closely linked together to create the strength of the Vietnamese people in life new era. So patriotism education is the process of consciously, purposefully and planned influencing the subjects of education to help their personality develop properly, helping them to love their homeland more and be loyal to them. Fatherland, have aspirations, take

positive actions to serve and bring benefits to the Fatherland and the People.

Educating national consciousness, arousing patriotism and pride in the historical traditions of our ancestors for the younger generation and teenagers is an urgent requirement. Especially in the current context, when science and technology is developing strongly, globalization and internationalization with subjective and objective factors having multi-dimensional impacts, it is even more necessary to strengthen the implementation of awareness education nationalism and patriotism among the young generation in a methodical and systematic way.

Today, international integration is the main trend, helping countries exchange for economic development and strongly promote resources for development. Through the process of economic exchange, countries learn a lot from each other, but from there, traditional cultural values and characteristics in each country and region gradually disappear. Promote the younger generation to integrate while still preserving national identity, so that each person remains a nucleus of national cultural values, and a subject in spreading Vietnamese national cultural values reaching the world is an urgent and long-term requirement.

After more than three decades of innovation, our country has achieved great achievements, many areas of development are considered miracles by the world. The path of innovation was opened in 1986 and the starting point was determined to be innovation in thinking, first of all economic thinking, which has promoted the transformation of the economic model from centralized bureaucratic subsidy to a centralized, subsidized bureaucratic model socialist-oriented market economy with a multi-sector economy, promoting democracy in the economy, overcoming all challenges, setting new premises and opportunities for the country's increasingly high development.

Vietnam's economy is considered to be highly open in the world. Specifically, the rapid increase in goods produced abroad is increasingly widespread in the market, to the point where it is difficult to distinguish the origin of the goods.

Even people are getting used to goods labeled as made in Vietnam but bearing international or foreign brand names; Domestically produced products cannot be distinguished from Vietnamese enterprises or foreign-invested enterprises. The innovation path has turned Vietnam into a low-middle income country, with people's living standards and quality of life increasingly improved and significantly enhanced. From one of the countries with the lowest income in the world, every year a part of the people seriously lacks food and basic necessities for life, Vietnam has risen to become a dynamic economy, a The country is a leading exporter of many agricultural products and actively contributes to the globalization process. The prestige and position of the nation and nation are enhanced in the international arena.

The Solution Contributes to Enhancing Patriotism among Today's Students

Firstly, arouse self-respect and national pride in the young generation. Integration and development open up opportunities to arouse patriotism and national pride. Today's youth are part of an interconnected global youth culture, interconnected by arts and culture: music, film, fashion and technology. There are some things about traditional concepts about borders and countries that are no longer consistent with reality. Therefore, the expressions of patriotism that are not really strong among Vietnamese young people who were born abroad or have not really experienced deeply Vietnamese culture is also understandable.

Besides, the younger generation often takes the lead and responds well to changes around them. Being aware of the current demographics and attitudes of younger generations is important, as these characteristics will help us connect with them as they grow older. Therefore, from now on, we need to actively care and invest in the young generation so that they can understand the importance of patriotism and national pride. Vietnamese students are a young human resource, capable of creativity and innovation, playing an important role in building the economic, social and cultural foundation for the future. They are also the generation that

continues to build and protect traditional and revolutionary values, while participating in social activities for the benefit of the community and the country. At the same time, the solidarity, creativity and enthusiasm of students create the strength and development of the nation.

Second, patriotism education according to Ho Chi Minh's perspective must be associated with emulation, learning, building and protecting the homeland. In the struggle for national liberation, patriotism in his opinion is the struggle and self-sacrifice for the independence and freedom of the Fatherland. Today, patriotism is expressed in the actions of young people to promote their abilities, qualities, sense of self-study, self-creation, efforts in emulating, studying and training themselves to bring the country out of poverty and backwardness; At the same time, fight against the wrong ideas of hostile forces; fight against young people who are "infected" with the ideology of "foreign worship", follow a pragmatic lifestyle, and personally lose their self-worth and traditional national values. In order to promote the role of young people and promote the patriotic tradition according to his thoughts, it is even more necessary to educate patriotism associated with the ideology of emulation, learning and building protecting the homeland and country.

To improve the effectiveness of educating young people on patriotism according to Ho Chi Minh's viewpoint in the current period, it is necessary to promote propaganda for officials, party members, youth and families to be more aware of the concept. The position and role of patriotism education according to Ho Chi Minh's perspective needs to combine education from family, school, organizations, unions and the whole society.

Third, it is necessary to innovate the content and methods of education. In the context of international integration and new goals and requirements, the content of patriotism and national consciousness education needs to change, focusing on educating the young generation about traditional national cultural knowledge, helps the young generation deeply understand and realize the cultural values,

history and national traditions. Equipping students with knowledge about history, culture and national traditions, while encouraging pride and patriotism will contribute to building a united society and sustainable development.

Educating national consciousness as well as arousing patriotism in the young generation is not easy. Educational methods need to constantly innovate to be appropriate. Specifically, for students, it is necessary to integrate national awareness education into the knowledge learning program and extracurricular activities. Educating national consciousness is not simply about learning about ethnicity in books, but needs to create real-life experiences and combine them with practical activities in society. Learning about and participating in cultural activities, traditional festivals and community projects will help students better understand their homeland, national spirit and become active and responsible citizens responsibility.

Fourth, patriotism education according to Ho Chi Minh's perspective is to be attached to the people, wholeheartedly serve the People, and serve the Fatherland. Patriotism among young people must be expressed in accordance with His teachings: loyalty to the Fatherland, wholeheartedly serving the People, knowing how to love the people and taking the people as the root, having sincere feelings, knowing how to be excited fight and sacrifice for the Fatherland and for the People. Ho Chi Minh taught the young generation to "love the Fatherland, love fellow citizens". Educating young people must cultivate and train themselves in revolutionary ethics: "diligence, frugality, integrity, righteousness, public-mindedness, and impartiality". Those are the four virtues of humans, "without one virtue, one cannot become a human being", as well as "Heaven has four seasons, earth has four directions, without one season one cannot become heaven, without one direction one cannot become earth."

Conclusion

Patriotism is a precious tradition of the Vietnamese people. Patriotism is passed down from generation to generation, it has penetrated deeply into the subconscious of Vietnamese people. Patriotism, idealistic enlightenment, the will to be self-reliant and not willing to accept poverty or backwardness are the factors that create strong political courage for young people, helping them overcome difficulties and challenges, repelling trivial material temptations and destructive actions that divide young people by hostile forces. Patriotic education for young people requires regular, continuous and closely linked to the development process and practical situation of the country.

References

- Dong, N.T. (2022). *Educating patriotism and national consciousness for today's Vietnamese youth*. Central website of Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union.
- Lac, N.V. (2020). *Educating patriotism according to Ho Chi Minh's ideology for young people in the current period*. Bac Lieu: Chau Van Dang School of Politics.
- Linh, N.T. (2024). *Educating national consciousness and patriotism for the young generation of Vietnam in building and developing the country and international integration*. Khanh Hoa Propaganda.
- Minh, H.M. (2011). *Complete works*. Hanoi: National Political Publishing House.
- Sieng, N.C. (2024), Educating patriotism for Vietnamese students according to Ho Chi Minh's ideology. *Journal of Politics and Development*.
- Thao, L.T.M. (2017). *Educating patriotism for Vietnamese youth today*.